

Delivering HS2 and Euston — Written Evidence

House of Commons Public Accounts Committee

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This submission does not contest the case for HS2 or the merits of the December 2024 programme reset. It addresses a narrower question within the Committee's scope: why cost, scope and benefit uncertainty has persisted for over a decade, and what governance architecture would prevent its recurrence. The recurring failures the Committee has documented since 2013 are properties of the programme's governance architecture, not the conduct of any individual or organisation. The trajectory from the £20.5bn Phase 1 estimate of 2012 (Cabinet Office, 2026) to the 19 May 2026 cost-and-schedule reset range of £87.7bn–£102.7bn in 2025 prices — first services not before 2036, the full Euston scheme not before 2040 (Department for Transport et al., 2026a, 2026b) — is not a sequence of estimating errors. The Department now attributes about two-thirds of the overrun to "*past misunderstanding of the work required, underestimation and inefficiency*" and one-third to inflation not previously factored in (Department for Transport et al., 2026a): itself a structural finding, not a cost report. It is the predictable signature of an architecture that fixes scope and budget before uncertainty is resolved, then manages deviation reactively. The reset is the moment to correct the architecture, not only the numbers.

This analysis is deliberately technocratic. It takes the governance architecture as its object and sets aside the political economy of major-project decisions: the judgement over which programmes to begin, continue, pause or stop is legitimate, can override any governance design, and rests with ministers and the Committee, not the author. The aim is to specify the architecture within which that judgement is exercised, so that political decisions are taken against an explicit and current picture rather than a decayed one.

This submission builds on the Stewart (2025) and Lovegrove (Cabinet Office, 2026) reviews, which identify capability, accountability and audit deficits in the existing model. The argument here is complementary: Lovegrove's Recommendation 12b (Accounting Officers' analysis of multi-decadal cost, risk and benefit) and Recommendation 16 (intervention options at all delivery stages) call for an architectural shift that the review identifies; this submission specifies it.

How the programme is responding to change and managing risks

The core structural fault is a mismatch between the duration of the commitment and the validity horizon of its underpinning assumptions. HS2 commits public resources across decades, but the demand forecasts, cost models, and benefit assumptions on which those commitments rest stay credible for only a few years. An architecture that locks scope and budget at sanction, then treats every later deviation as a variance to be explained, has no way to re-baseline as uncertainty resolves. The result is a programme structurally surprised by its own progress. Even before the April 2020 Notice to Proceed, the National Audit Office had seen the pattern: estimates outrun by events, the 2026 opening no longer feasible (National Audit Office, 2020).

The distinction between variance management and re-baselining is not semantic. Variance management asks why the outturn departs from the original plan and seeks to bring it back; it treats the sanction-stage estimate as ground truth and every later figure as an error. Re-baselining accepts that the sanction-stage estimate was the least-informed forecast the programme would ever produce, and that the right baseline is the one current evidence supports. The Lovegrove review reaches the same conclusion in a different language: Civil Service teams failed to *"recognise the scale of the remaining intrinsic risk in the project"* and instead made *"substantial, but ultimately incremental, adjustments to an existing picture"* (Cabinet Office, 2026). A decade of escalating estimates is what variance management produces when the original baseline was, predictably, optimistic: each revision lands as a shock rather than the routine resolution of uncertainty it is.

Optimism bias here is not a failure of individual diligence. The Treasury's own Green Book mandates optimism-bias uplifts precisely because cost and schedule under-estimation in

major projects is systematic and predictable (HM Treasury, 2026). The record across global megaprojects — Flyvbjerg's "iron law": over budget, over time, under benefits, again and again — confirms this is the base rate, not the exception (Flyvbjerg, 2014; Flyvbjerg et al., 2003). Lovegrove's own list of HS2's "*original sins*" — gold-plating of the high-speed concept, main works contracts let at insufficient design maturity, "*the level of costs and risk being very badly underestimated*" (Cabinet Office, 2026) — describes optimism bias operating through the architecture, not individual carelessness. Where a binary commit-or-cancel model rewards inclusion in the portfolio, every promoter has an incentive to forecast optimistically as the price of sanction (Flyvbjerg, 2014). The bias is manufactured by the architecture; exhorting individuals to be more realistic cannot correct it.

The 2023 cancellation of Phase 2 shows how the absence of an intermediate governance state turns a manageable problem into a cliff-edge. With no mechanism to pause, stage or de-scope a section while preserving its option value, the only instruments were full continuation or outright cancellation after heavy sunk commitment. Sunk commitment of that scale pulls toward continuation — the escalation of commitment Staw (1976) documented — so a programme that can only commit or cancel will, under fiscal pressure, eventually cancel abruptly, stranding prior investment and the integrated benefit case alike. Lovegrove's Recommendation 16, that the government should "*more actively consider its leverage to intervene*" at all delivery stages with "*tolerances for performance deviation and mitigation plans*" (Cabinet Office, 2026), reaches the same conclusion; the intermediate states it would require are what this submission specifies. Responding to change needs governance states between "proceed" and "stop"; HS2's architecture has not provided them.

What progress has been made to improve governance and integration arrangements

There has been genuine and welcome progress. The December 2024 reset, the Stewart and Lovegrove reviews, the Transport Secretary's 19 May 2026 statement setting out a revised cost range and schedule and cutting operating speed to 320 kph (Department for Transport et al., 2026a), and the restructure of HS2 Ltd — 300 back-office roles cut, 168 oversight, cost-management and decision-support roles added — together represent the most substantial governance recalibration the programme has yet undergone. The intent to confront the true

position rather than defend an untenable forecast is the right foundation for recovery, and the Committee should recognise it.

The structural concern is that this adaptive capacity rests on crisis salience and individual leadership rather than being a standing property of the architecture. Adaptive governance that switches on only at a public crisis is not resilience; it is rescue. The test for the Committee is whether the new arrangements will keep re-baselining cost, scope and risk on a routine cycle once political and media attention moves on, or whether the programme will again drift from sanction to the next crisis with no scheduled re-examination in between. The reviews to date are episodic, not routine, and the later ones crisis-triggered: Oakervee (Department for Transport & High Speed Two (HS2) Limited, 2020) at sanction, then Stewart (2025) and Lovegrove (Cabinet Office, 2026) in response to escalating cost disclosures. A system that produces a major external review at sanction and again only after a fourfold cost increase (Cabinet Office, 2026) does not re-baseline; it audits failure.

Integration remains the visible weak point, and Euston is its sharpest expression. The Committee's February 2024 report found the Department had no plan to attract the private finance on which the Euston scheme depended (Committee of Public Accounts, 2024). An unresolved funding model at the programme's most complex interface is not merely a financing gap; it is an integration risk that propagates through the design, phasing and benefit case of the whole southern section. A station whose funding is undecided cannot have a stable design, and that instability runs back up the line.

Where the sponsor (the Department) and the delivery body (HS2 Ltd) hold different estimates and risk appetites — as the divergent November 2023 and June 2024 ranges suggest — the interface between them becomes a source of uncertainty in itself. Lovegrove documents the mechanism directly: the Senior Responsible Owner attended HS2 Ltd board meetings only as a *"DfT Observer"* until the 2020 Notice to Proceed, and the company developed *"an excessive and ultimately false sense of independence"* while *"the expected commercial discipline and shareholder challenge to live within agreed cost envelopes did not materialise"* (Cabinet Office, 2026). Two institutions holding parallel numbers will, under pressure, each defend the figure that protects its position, and reconcile only in crisis. The divergence is not only positional. The delivery company holds the construction reality; the Department and ministers hold the fiscal and demand reality. Even in good faith, neither sees the whole alone. Effective integration governance, therefore, needs a reconciled baseline —

jointly owned by the Department's Accounting Officer and the Senior Responsible Owner — and revised on a fixed cycle, with a clear allocation of which body carries which risk. That cycle is the occasion on which the two partial pictures are forced together, rather than left to meet in crisis. The question for the Committee is not whether the two organisations co-operate, but whether they answer to one shared set of numbers.

Whether appropriate arrangements are in place to achieve value for money, manage community impact and realise benefits

Value-for-money assessment here rests on benefit-cost ratios from discounted cash-flow projections running decades ahead. Lovegrove identifies the same problem from the opposite direction: Accounting Officer assessments treated full Phase 1 plus Phase 2 delivery as the value-for-money baseline when Phase 2 designs were *"much less mature"* than Phase 1, and contingency presented as covering *"70–75% of comparable projects"* created a *"false sense of security"* (Cabinet Office, 2026). Recommendation 12b accordingly asks HM Treasury to clarify how Accounting Officers can appropriately analyse the *"full nature of the costs, risks and benefits"* of multi-decadal programmes (Cabinet Office, 2026) — the question this section takes up. Under deep uncertainty, a single best-estimate forecast over several decades is fragile: small revisions to demand growth, discount rate or delivery date swing the headline ratio across the threshold of acceptability. A more robust basis for periodic judgement is to complement this with a Cost of Delay test — assessing the value foregone for each year the capability is delayed (Reinertsen, 2009; Shabad et al., 2026). This needs only a defensible near-term judgement about the cost of not yet having the capability, not a thirty-year benefit projection no one believes.

A further distortion operates through how the expenditure is classified. Where public budgeting treats capital and operational spending under different rules, it builds in a standing bias toward the capital-intensive option — regardless of whether a smaller, incremental or operational alternative would deliver a comparable share of the benefit at lower irreversibility. The point is not that incremental alternatives were preferable for HS2; rather, the appraisal architecture did not test the capital commitment against them on equal terms, and future assessment should require it.

Benefits realisation is treated as a one-off product fixed at sanction, not a flow tracked and re-baselined as the programme changes. When Phase 2 was cancelled, the integrated benefit case — predicated on the full network — was voided, yet the commitment to Phase 1 persisted against a benefit case that no longer described what would be built. The Committee's February 2025 report reached an adjacent conclusion, calling the programme "*a casebook example of how not to run a major project*" (Committee of Public Accounts, 2025). This is a stranded benefit case: expenditure justified by benefits the revised scope cannot deliver. Without a mechanism that re-baselines benefits alongside cost whenever scope changes, value-for-money figures detach from the project actually under construction.

Community impact is governed as if disruption were an event rather than a duration. Blight, severance and construction disruption fall continuously across the delivery horizon, but mitigation and compensation are largely indexed to the schedule assumed at sanction. Each slip therefore lengthens the period over which affected communities bear uncompensated cost, with no automatic adjustment. An architecture that re-baselines cost and benefits but not community impact externalises the consequences of its own delay onto the people least able to influence it.

Summary and recommendations

The failures the Committee has documented since 2013 — unknown cost, undefined scope, uncertain timeline, unclear benefits — are not separate lapses. They are the coherent output of a governance architecture built for a certainty that megaprojects do not possess. The reset, with the Stewart and Lovegrove reviews, is the chance to replace that architecture rather than re-forecast within it. The five recommendations below are architectural specifications complementary to Lovegrove's seventeen: where Lovegrove addresses *who* should govern and *with what capabilities*, these address *how* the system should re-baseline, decide and exit under deep uncertainty.

- 1. Replace binary commit-or-cancel governance with a staged three-state architecture.** The programme and its remaining decision points should be governed through explicit Active, Standby and Exit states, with defined annual review triggers and transition criteria (Shabad et al., 2026). A Standby state preserves option value while halting new capital commitments, allowing a section to be paused on evidence

rather than cancelled in crisis. Had it existed, Phase 2 could have been a managed transition, not a cliff-edge. These are the intermediate intervention states Lovegrove Recommendation 16 implies.

- 2. Re-baseline cost, scope and risk on a fixed annual cycle, not on crisis.** The Department and HS2 Ltd should maintain a single reconciled baseline — owned jointly by the Department's Accounting Officer and the Senior Responsible Owner — revised on a scheduled annual cycle independent of political attention. Lovegrove's Recommendation 16 already points the way: in asking for "*tolerances for performance deviation*", it names the instrument an adaptive programme needs, and those tolerances become the cycle's second trigger. The cycle should run on two: a fixed annual review that happens even when no figure has moved, and an out-of-cycle review fired when a monitored signal — cost, schedule, scope or demand — crosses a pre-set tolerance, at which point the delivery body re-baselines early rather than waiting for the calendar. A scheduled floor without tolerances makes the programme wait up to a year while a known divergence widens; tolerances without a floor let quiet drift accumulate unflagged. This is a baseline cycle, not a funding cycle: scheduled re-baselining is the precondition for a long-term funding control period — as operated for Network Rail and identified by Stewart (2025) as absent for HS2 — and converts the adaptive capacity now visible under reset leadership from a one-off rescue into a standing property of the system.
- 3. Make optimism-bias correction structural and independent.** Each annual re-baseline should face an independent challenge using reference-class forecasting against comparable completed projects, consistent with the Treasury's own guidance (Flyvbjerg, 2014; HM Treasury, 2026). This addresses *supply-side* optimism — cost and schedule underestimation — for which reference-class forecasting and disciplined front-end planning are the established corrective measures (Flyvbjerg & Gardner, 2023). Recommendation 4 addresses the complementary *demand-side* failure: the assumption that the value proposition justifying the sanction stays valid across a decade-long delivery. Lovegrove's Recommendations 6 and 13, on a "*well resourced and sophisticated*" internal audit function and clearer assurance roles, address where the challenge sits; this addresses the method. Independent challenge at a fixed point removes the incentive to forecast optimistically and makes correction a process, not an appeal to individual realism.

4. **Introduce a Cost of Delay test to complement the benefit-cost ratio for periodic continuation decisions.** In addition to the benefit-cost ratio, the Department should assess continued expenditure against a simpler periodic measure: the value foregone for each year the capability is delayed. This Cost of Delay test needs only a defensible near-term judgement, not a thirty-year benefit projection no one believes, and provides a more robust basis for periodic decisions when the long-range forecast is itself deeply uncertain (Reinertsen, 2009). It is a concrete answer to the question Lovegrove Recommendation 12b puts to HM Treasury.
5. **Track benefits and community impact as flows, re-baselined with scope.** Any scope change should automatically trigger a published revision of both the benefit case and the community-impact and compensation envelope, the latter indexed to actual rather than assumed delivery duration. This prevents a stranded benefit case and stops the delay from being silently externalised onto affected communities.

References

- Cabinet Office. (2026). *Lovegrove Review: The implications for the Civil Service and wider public sector of findings of the James Stewart Review*.
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/lovegrove-review-the-implications-for-the-civil-service-and-wider-public-sector-of-findings-of-the-james-stewart-review>
- Committee of Public Accounts. (2024). *HS2 and Euston. Tenth Report of Session 2023–24* (HC 67). House of Commons Library.
<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/43184/documents/214904/default/>
- Committee of Public Accounts. (2025). *HS2: Update following the Northern leg cancellation. Tenth Report of Session 2024–25* (HC 357). House of Commons Library.
<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/46679/documents/239132/default/>
- Department for Transport, & High Speed Two (HS2) Limited. (2020). *Oakervee Review of HS2*.
<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5e5f6d6d86650c5143547885/oakervee-review.pdf>

Department for Transport, High Speed Two (HS2) Limited, & Alexander, H. (2026a). *Oral statement to Parliament. HS2 reset*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/hs2-reset>

Department for Transport, High Speed Two (HS2) Limited, & Alexander, H. (2026b). *Written statement to Parliament. HS2 6-monthly report to Parliament: May 2026*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/hs2-6-monthly-report-to-parliament-may-2026>

Flyvbjerg, B. (2014). What you Should Know about Megaprojects and Why: An Overview. *Project Management Journal*, 45(2), 6–19. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pmj.21409>

Flyvbjerg, B., Bruzelius, N., & Rothengatter, W. (2003). *Megaprojects and Risk: An Anatomy of Ambition*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107050891>

Flyvbjerg, B., & Gardner, D. (2023). *How Big Things Get Done: The Surprising Factors Behind Every Successful Project, from Home Renovations to Space Exploration*. Pan Macmillan.

HM Treasury. (2026). *The Green Book. UK Government Guidance On Appraisal*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-green-book-appraisal-and-evaluation-in-central-government/the-green-book-2026>

National Audit Office. (2020). *High Speed Two: A progress update* (HC 40). <https://www.nao.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/High-Speed-Two-A-progress-update.pdf>

Reinertsen, D. G. (2009). *The Principles of Product Development Flow: Second Generation Lean Product Development*. Celeritas Publishing.

Shabad, V., Yusupov, R., & Ivanov, K. (2026). *Technology Investment Governance Under Deep Uncertainty: The Case for Annual Portfolio Models in Public Infrastructure* (6469862). SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6469862>

Staw, B. M. (1976). Knee-deep in the big muddy: a study of escalating commitment to a chosen course of action. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 16(1), 27–44. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(76\)90005-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(76)90005-2)

Stewart, J. (2025). *Stewart Review. Major Transport Projects Governance and Assurance Review: The HS2 Experience*.
<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/68a72b319e1cebdd2c96a0ae/hs2-experience-major-transport-projects-governance-assurance-review.pdf>

Declarations

AI use: During the preparation of this submission, the author used Claude (Anthropic) to improve readability and language quality as a non-native English speaker. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content and takes full responsibility for the content of this submission.

Competing interests: The author has no current financial interest in the outcome of this inquiry. The author is a co-author of the academic work cited in this submission (Shabad et al., 2026).